

COLLECTIVE MECHANISMS TO COMPENSATE VICTIMS OF TERRORIST CRIMES

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Abstract

Today, the world is witnessing an unparalleled escalation in terrorist operations, in which civilians of all ages are often victims, and perhaps what Iraq witnessed in the recent period of terrorist operations carried out by ISIS and accepted by al-Qaeda is the best evidence of that, so in the absence of ability The perpetrators of these crimes must pay compensation for many reasons. Either because the perpetrator of these crimes is unknown or has been killed, the primary responsibility for compensation lies with the state, as it is obligated to compensate the victims for the damage they sustained as a result of terrorist operations, and we have indicated in this letter To the issue of the state's responsibility in compensation and its amount, as well as to address the collective mechanisms of compensation(Insurance and Guarantee Funds), which we focused on in an integrated chapter, and which we call on the Iraqi legislator to explicitly adopt them by stipulating them in the laws because these mechanisms have a very important role in compensating the victims of terrorist crimes as they urgently replace the perpetrator of the crime in the face of the victim and this is limited The same constitutes an important guarantee in ensuring compensation for those affected by terrorist crimes.

Keywords: Terrorism - Collective mechanisms- compensation- insurance-victims of terrorism.

Introduction

There is no doubt that terrorist operations are a source of many damages to civilians.

1. The importance of study

The topic of research is of great importance and this importance stems from the fact that it deals with the subject of (mechanisms to compensate victims of terrorist crimes, collective mechanisms as a model) as it is necessary to address such topics in order to indicate the mechanisms available and their effectiveness on the one hand, and because this topic constitutes a modern hour in view of the large number of terrorist operations and their expansion until they have acquired an international character, so it is important and in light of the many victims of these operations to address this issue.

2. Justifications and reasons for choosing the subject of the study

There are many reasons why this topic was chosen, including:

1. The increase in terrorist operations and the resulting increase in the number of victims requires that mechanisms be shown to compensate them for the damage done to them.
2. The desire to highlight the role of collective mechanisms in compensating victims of terrorist operations.
3. Deficiencies in the treatments available to compensate for terrorist operations.

3. The problem of study

The problem with the study is to highlight efforts to compensate victims of terrorist operations in order to demonstrate their effectiveness, not to mention the role played by collective mechanisms in this regard, with a view to outlining the most important shortcomings in this subject and proposing ways to address them.

4. Study hypothesis

The research hypothesis is based on the basic point that traditional mechanisms do not help compensate victims of terrorist crimes, so it is necessary to adopt collective mechanisms that play an important and effective role in this area.

5. Study methodology

In writing this research, we relied on an analytical approach that relies on analyzing the legal texts relevant to the subject of research as well as addressing the content of collective mechanisms in order to highlight their effectiveness in compensating terrorist victims and highlighting their shortcomings, eventually trying to develop some proposals that would create more feasible mechanisms for compensating victims of terrorist operations.

1.1 The concept of the victim in terrorist crimes

Researching the victim's concept of terrorist crimes requires us to address the definition of the victim and thus distinguish him from what he suspects, so we have divided this research into two demands as follows:

1.1.1 Definition of victim

The definition of victims of terrorist acts is important, whether in international criminal law or national criminal law, because the purpose of defining a victim is to identify groups who may benefit from rights recognized by international criminal law and national laws.

With regard to international treaties and resolutions, they played a prominent role in defining the victim, and although Rome's provision did not address the basis of the 1998 Criminal Court to define the victim, he left the matter to the rules of procedure and evidence, which defined the victim as "persons of nature affected by the commission of any crime within the jurisdiction of the Court."

The definition of victims in the Universal Declaration of the Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power is also stated: "Persons who have suffered individual or collective harm from terrorist crime, including physical or mental harm, psychological suffering, economic loss or significant deprivation of their fundamental rights through terrorist acts".

As for The Iraqi Penal Code No. 111 of 1969, the Code of Criminal Procedure Assets No. 23 of 1971, they were not defined by the concept of the victim, but the term "victim" was mentioned in the Law on Due Process and without clearly defining the term, as stated in the Law on Compensation of Victims as a result of hostilities, military mistakes and terrorist

operations No. 20 of 2009, which he defined in its first article as: "Every natural person has been harmed by hostilities, military mistakes and terrorist operations." The question arises in this context: can the victim of the crime be considered the victim or the victim of the crime? According to a trend of jurisprudence, the victim of the crime is the victim who has suffered harm, whether natural or moral, and in the latter case he may be a public person and may be a private person, given that society as a whole is considered to be a victim of the crime along with the individual victim, if the crime occurs on his security, system and stability.

2. The role of collective mechanisms in compensating victims of terrorist crimes

The development towards objective responsibility has been one of the means used by the judiciary in order to provide effective protection to those affected in general, but this development did not stop there, did not respond to the aspirations of the victims in their ambulance, but this subject develops the law and continues to develop proves that it is always able to keep pace with the movement of human life continuing the development that led to the emergence of new legal systems that have been produced towards strengthening the protection of victims even with the absence of error and even with the absence of responsibility These collectively worded systems are manifested in various forms, including insurance and the establishment of security funds, in order to activate the role of the State in the area of equity for victims, in general and victims of terrorist acts in particular .

1.2 The concept of collective mechanisms

Some have pointed out that the social responsibility in the modern era means that the social body seeks by all means to achieve appropriate compensation for damages to the individual without adhering to the dictates of individual responsibility to abide by its principles () whether responsibility based on error or those based solely on theoretical harm risks on one side or even adherence to limiting the obligation to compensation to liability on the other, especially if we know that the purpose of compensation is not to punish the side as much as What is the reparation of the damage done to the injured. As the jurist savatier commented on collective responsibility, he says that the jurisprudence of objective responsibility has been transformed to confirm its objectives and purpose, even if it is on the ruins of the law of responsibility , by supporting that objectivity through the obligation to compensate and not through the basis of liability until the injured person finds him a collective obligation to commit his direction to compensation besides the injured or instead, and this collective obligation is based not on the basis of the obligation of society to compensate all respect through collective compensation systems. This is after the trend in time became to protect the victim (injured) and enable him to obtain compensation for the damage he suffered easily and easily. This is because the law as the twin of society has been produced and continues to be produced from the systems that preserve the continuity of the establishment of society, it modifies systems to blame them and the constant variables responsible for the movement of life, which is a fundamental feature of change and since the physical integrity of the human being and the protection of innate social requirements close to the continuation of human life have threatened the terrible dangers of modern harm, this has led to the expansion of objective responsibility in various forms and by

presenting the opinions of jurists in the definition of collective responsibility possible. Come up with the following results:

1. The burden of compensating victims at its origin rests primarily with the individual responsible in accordance with traditional rules of responsibility.
2. If the victim exhausts all the traditional rules of liability, he has no choice but to rely on collective systems for compensation.
3. The importance and urgent need of collective systems to compensate for the bodily harm that individual defendants are difficult to bear through the extraordinary damage caused by terrorist crimes is evident, where they find their meaning and achieve their objectives (collective regimes) in this context, i.e. in the context of terrorist crimes and the destruction they cause.

1.1.2 Image of collective mechanisms and their role in compensating victims of terrorist crimes

The collective mechanisms for the disbursement of compensation to victims have taken various forms, while some legislation has established funds for the fulfilment of compensatory purposes, including the French legislator, to bring other legislation into the insurance system to eventually bring these images to the same end: to ensure the right of victims of terrorist crimes to compensation quickly and effectively.

2.1.2 Insurance as a means of compensating victims of terrorism

Insurance has become an important role in modern societies in the face of its multiplicity of types to cover aspects of activities, except to try to cover the development in various areas of life and the dangers it needs from associated responsibilities and the emergence of new risks such as the dangers of defective products as well as the dangers of pollution and the dangers of terrorist crimes, since these risks are characterized by very serious damage and civil responsibility in general has been affected in its essence or content as a result of the data witnessed by society at the beginning of the industrial revolution and the end of the information revolution. The emergence of groups spreading their economic activity in society such as companies and associations has led to the need to seek a new form of cooperation between these associations and their employees aimed at avoiding the damage to the group and transforming the civil liability system from its original employee, which is a means of deterring dangers and reparation to a compensatory function so that the responsibility of the specialist is secured. In France there have been many attempts to insure the dangers of terrorism despite the reluctance of some insurance companies in this area as we will see if Research into insurance work in the field of rapid and effective compensation for victims of terrorist crimes requires us to determine what insurance in general is held by parties and arranges effects according to certain conditions and then to look at the technical and legal insurance and the extent to which it applies to the dangers of terrorism.

2.2 Insurance Definition

The insurance has sparked a major doctrinal debate, and part of the jurisprudence has defined it as "a process whereby one of the parties, who is insured for a fee, receives the premium on the obligation of the other party, which is the insurer, in the interest of the security or third parties when achieving a certain risk, and the insurer takes responsibility for a set of risks that are cleared in accordance with the laws of statistics."

Another aspect of jurisprudence defined it as "a contract under which the insurer is obliged to lead to the insured or to the beneficiary for whom the insurance is required for an amount or income arranged or other financial compensation in the case and type of incident insured or to achieve the risk described in the contract, in exchange for a specified amount or periodic instalments that the insured provides to the insured" and as long as the insurance process includes two aspects, one of which is legal related to the relationship of the insured insured, which the previous definition succeeded in standing The second is based on a campaign of technical rules and foundations related to statistics and the many laws that the insurance contract does not envisage without it, otherwise the content of this contract is a prohibited process contained in gambling or a bet, which is the aspect that was overlooked by the previous definition . Insurance is a contract that obliges the insurer to lead to the insured or to the beneficiary a sum of money or a salary income or any other financial compensation in the event of the accident insured against him in exchange for instalments or any other payment made by the insured to the insured" through the above we find that the Iraqi legislator dealt only with the legal aspect and did not address the technical aspect, but the Egyptian legislator knew the insurance through article (747) of the Egyptian civil law in force where He pointed out that insurance is intended "a contract that obliges the insurer to lead to the insured or to the beneficiary whose insurance is required in his favour amounts of status or salary income or any other financial compensation in the event of an accident or achieve the risk described in the contract in exchange for a premium or any other payment made by the insured insured", he notes on this definition that the Egyptian legislator has highlighted the legal aspect on the technical and higher side and made some kind of conformity between those multiple aspects while The French legislator did not know the insurance contract under the provisions of the French Insurance Act No. 5 of January 7, 1981 .

1.2.2 The extent to which the risks of terrorist crimes are vulnerable to insurance coverage

The insurance philosophy is based on trying to expand the circle of shareholders in providing financial security to pay the compensation due when individuals are exposed to enormous damages that are too great to bear, as through insurance the loss can be dispersed and squandered by the presence of a large number of people who are all threatened by one risk so that once this risk is achieved against one of them has been compensated by the amounts of collaborators ().

First: The legal extent to which the risks of terrorist crimes are legally insured:

The risk is the main focus of insurance as a supposed element that the insurance wisher should fortify himself from its financial effects, and in doing so is considered as the shop to which the insurance contract is answered, which makes the latter depend on the existence of the risk and then that other elements of insurance, namely the value of insurance and in exchange for insurance are closely related to the risk insured, that the risk in the insurance sense shares with the risk in the general sense in the sense that it is possible, which means that a future event is not Certainly the occurrence is subject to accident and these dangerous characteristics that must be available in order to be insured as the term danger to the incident may occur and limit the obligations arising from the incident, the danger insured in terrorist acts is the incident that occurs as a result of the terrorist act, which constitutes an unspecified act that occurs in advance and does not depend on examining the will of the believer or believer. The danger in general is the justification and the direct reason for which the insurance contract was established, and therefore the risk is to attack the insured, who are the victim of terrorist incidents, and this risk is not realized.

The risk should be potential and not depend on the sole will of a contractor:

1. The risk of terrorist acts should be:

The essence of the idea of danger is probability, uncertainty and probability that fall between two limits: the limit of impossibility and the limit of certainty, when an event is considered an insurance risk that must come out of the confirmation area. Since terrorist crimes are aimed at striking public order and bringing down innocent people, regardless of their religion, nationality or age, and without discrimination, the activities of terrorist groups undoubtedly constitute potential incidents that can occur at any time, as they are not achievable so that they are likely to occur, fall, bear or bear their type. A personal criterion and therefore the mere feeling of a person's possibility and type of terrorist attack is not considered a risk worth insure, but it is the party that influenced the risk resulting from this attack that allows insurance, as the terrorist risk is in fact incidents that occur in pre-known circumstances and are outside any future expectations and the resulting damage, which changes according to the circumstances, cannot be expected in every case, place and time from which the terrorist attack occurred. The losses resulting from placing explosives inside a school or will not be the same as those that may occur as a result of the assault on a person or some person using a weapon, the extent of which is the largest and most serious loss to persons or property.

2. The risks of terrorist acts do not depend on the will of contractors:

The danger must depend on an external order from the will of one or both of the disabled in order to be insured in the sense that this danger is subject to coincidence that applies to the nature of terrorist crimes, since most of the victims of terrorist crimes are people who have been bad luck and bad luck in the midst of events. A possible number of victims, regardless of their positions, levels, gender or nationality, in order to draw the attention of local and international public opinion to his project or the organizing project to which he belongs.

Therefore, the victims of terrorist crimes are victims by chance, which makes the dangers resulting from those crimes apply to the property of being an insurance shop subject to accident. Second hand (). Here the question arises: do people believe in themselves, believe in their money, or both against the most serious terrorist crimes they may want? In limiting insurance to the dangers that affect money, terrorist crimes are equal to fire, theft or force majeure, such as earthquakes and floods, so there is room for the insured to return to fraudulent methods in his contribution to the danger insured, such as burning the house or shop, and attributing it to the terrorist attack and its insured dangers in order to obtain compensation, but insurance companies are supposed to have a group of experts who play an important role in standing up. The extent to which the insured contributes to the proof of the insured act of it.

Second: The technical foundations of insurance and the extent to which it applies to terrorist threats

Insurance is based on technical grounds, all of which aim to achieve solidarity between a group of individuals who are exposed to one risk or similar risks and to clear them in accordance with the laws of statistics . Cooperation is carried out between the total insured in order to protect them from a risk that threatens them by paying an amount of insurance value representing the premium to the insured who contributes to the integration of cooperation between this group with the intention of insurance from the danger to any of them, provided that the insured undertakes a certain performance when the insurance risk is realized. The insurance company clears the potential risk pool and conducts such clearing between them in accordance with the statistical laws.

2.2.2 The possibility of adopting the idea of insurance against the dangers of terrorist operations

It should be noted that the principle of liability has become incapable of ensuring effective protection of individuals, and to avoid this deficit there has been a urgent need for a supplementary system of liability that stands side by side with it, and this has been done through the development of the means of financial security, which is the idea of the insurance system, and these compensation funds will provide some kind of legal cover where they will work on the basis of the principle of legal solutions in the event of damage to compensation caused by terrorist operations, and therefore we will work to clarify the legal nature of the contract insurance, and then show the legal implications.

First: The legal nature of the insurance contract:

The issue of protecting those affected by the dangers of terrorist operations has become one of the most important problems looking for solutions, especially as it threatens the entity of society, as most countries have moved towards the search for ways to help bear the effects of these dangers in the event of their occurrence, thus guiding the human mind to the insurance system, which works to assess the nature of the risk and determine its magnitude and the extent to which it can be covered and the fragmentation of the effects of those dangers as well as distributing them to a large number of people in society so that they do not Leaving these effects concentrated solely on the person affected, i.e. the insurance aims to transfer all the

costs of repairing the damage to the total insurers and thus to ensure the safety of the insured, which is thus a useful solution to the problems of partial bankruptcy to which the injured person may be exposed and this means is a deterrent against administrative risks and is a preventive effect against negligence . The U.S. government has also provided sector support to insurance companies to enable them to accept coverage of terrorist acts after the U.S. Congress passed the Terrorism Insurance Act, and the U.S. government promised to compensate insurance companies, especially since the damage was very serious as the amount was \$100 billion in the event of terrorist attacks similar to those of September 11, 2001, as these attacks caused the biggest loss of the insurance industry in the world. Insurance companies alone are unable to cover the damage caused by terrorist acts of this magnitude.

France has also adopted the same approach and has adapted and developed the rules on the insurance contract so that it can be covered and the application of statistics factors, especially after terrorist operations have become a widespread global phenomenon, and therefore the individual and society alike must be protected against the risks to which they are exposed, as well as the volume of capital invested in this area, which is an economic resource for many companies, must be protected. Insurance against the risks resulting from terrorist operations is defined as a contract between the insured and the insured, who may be a natural or moral person through which the insured is obliged to perform the amount of insurance or compensation for the damage inflicted on the insured or his successor as a result of damage that falls into the content of the risks resulting from terrorist operations. It should be noted that terrorist crimes result in serious serious risks that the largest companies may be unable to take it upon themselves to cover all the risks resulting from them, and therefore must be fragmented, which as a result leads to a doubling of their number so that they exceed the capacity of the national market and require foreign participation, so collective insurance or the so-called merger of insurance companies is the best way to cover such risks, and the issue of the fragmentation of risks intended (reinsurance) is the best way to cover such risks.

Second: The effects of insurance against terrorist operations

In the beginning, we cannot fail to note the important fact that the contract for insurance against terrorist operations, like other insurance contracts, creates obligations and rights for the parties to the contract, and will only look into the obligations of the parties to the contract as follows:

1. Insurer's Obligations

It is recognized that there are a number of obligations on the part of the insurer (represented by the insurance company) and the obligation to perform the amount of insurance or the amount of compensation is one of the most important obligations of the insurer, which is decided by the Iraqi civil legislator in article (989) of the Iraqi Civil Code No. 40 of 1951, which states: "The insurer is obliged to compensate for the damage arising from the risk against him, but not to exceed the value of the insurance," through the above. Us: There is an obligation on the part of the insured, which is to compensate the injured person with a sum of money specified in the insurance policy by determining the value of the insured object and on the basis of which the insurance price is determined, and the document also guarantees the statement of the premium

that the insured is obliged to pay to the insured. The French legislator also stipulated in article (l. 113/5) of the French Insurance Act No. (5), issued on January 7, 1981. Based on the general provisions of the insurance contract, the insurance policy will be introduced against the dangers of terrorist operations.

2. The obligations of the insured

The second party to the insurance contract is represented by the insured, where it entails a number of obligations arising from the insurance contract in general, including those that are pre-risk, including those that are subsequent to its occurrence, and the obligation to pay the insurance premium is one of the most important obligations of the insured, as determined by article (986/1) of the iraqi civil law, which stipulates that "the insured abides by the following: A. Payment of premiums or other payments in the agreed term, these obligations are a general effect of the insurance contract, and there is an obligation on the insurer to take care, especially in insurance against terrorist operations, from important obligations that the insured must make in insurance against terrorist acts, and taking precautions is a material fact that can be proved by all legal means of proof."

Conclusion

At the end of this research, we have reached a set of findings and proposals, the most important of which will include:

First: Conclusions:

1. We have concluded that a terrorist crime is every criminal act by an individual or organized group to target individuals, groups or official or informal institutions that damage public and private property in order to disturb the security situation, stability and national unity, or to introduce terror, fear and panic among the people or to create chaos and to achieve terrorist purposes.
2. The victim of terrorist crimes is a person who is physically or morally harmed by terrorism and is often the most important person who has nothing to do with what the terrorist seeks in his terrorism, which requires compensation.
3. We also found that in limiting insurance to the dangers that affect money, terrorist crimes are equal to fire, theft or force majeure, such as earthquakes and floods, and therefore there is room for the insured to return to fraudulent methods in his contribution to the danger insured, such as burning the house or shop, and attributing it to the terrorist attack and its insured dangers in order to obtain compensation, but the insurance companies are supposed to have a group of experts who play an important role. In the field of finding out the extent to which the insured contributes to the proof of the act insured from him.

Second: recommendations:

1. We suggest that no specific or specific definition of terrorist crimes be adopted because adopting such a definition, no matter how much effort is made, will not be preventing and exhausting all forms of terrorism, therefore, relying on the description of acts that constitute

crimes will be better than definition, where all developments and developments in terrorist crime can be absorbed through description.

2. We recommend that the system of proactive enforcement of the law be adopted as a mechanism to reduce terrorist crimes, and this activation includes the international and national sides, which will undoubtedly reduce terrorist crimes and their risks and the resulting harm.

3. We call on the Iraqi legislature to explicitly adopt the idea of collective mechanisms as means of compensating victims of terrorist crimes because of the importance of compensating the victims for these crimes.

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